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Dr Ferreira (NF) is an Auxiliary Researcher at CIIMAR, experienced in applying different techniques at different organisational levels (from molecular to population) to understand the impacts of pollutants on ecosystems. NF's main focus is the application of 'Omics techniques to environmental and human toxicology based on Planetary Health principles. The results of his research have led to several practical outcomes that range from the application of new policies and measures to protect the environment and human populations to dissemination and co-working activities with schools, farmers and stakeholders, resulting in the solution of practical problems. NF has successfully obtained more than 3.5 M€ in grants and projects, received several awards and acted as a reviewer for different Funding programs.

A MULTI-OMICS APPROACH TO CAATINGA BEES: DIVING INTO GENE EXPRESSION, PESTICIDE TOLERANCE AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES ALTERATIONS

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14802546

Abstract

Pesticides pose serious threats to bees, impacting their health, reproduction, and even their role in ecosystem services (e.g., reduction of pollination processes, lower quality of the produced honey). These risks are multifaceted and can occur through various exposure routes (e.g., direct contact, contaminated food, residues in nesting places) and can disrupt bees' learning and memory. The Caatinga is a unique and biodiverse biome in the semi-arid region of Northeastern Brazil.

This biome is home to a rich bee fauna but also home to fruit farms responsible for 85% of Brazil's exports². To support the farmers' activity in the area that heavily relies on bee pollination, the effects of three commonly used pesticides, Lambda-cyhalothrin (insecticide), fenpyroximate (acaricide) and triflumizole (fungicide), on the transcriptomic responses of the bee species *Tetragonisca angustula* (jataí), *Melipona quadrifasciata* (mandaçaia) and *Nannotrigona testaceicornis* (iraí) to 50% of the recommended field application dose (rfad) through contaminated food. In addition, the impact of these pesticides on the gut microbiome was analysed. The results varied according to species and type of pesticide. Nonetheless, the common point was that all species exposed to 50% rfad impacted several pathways. Identically, the gut microbiome of these organisms was also impacted by all pesticides. These impacts can alter bees' immune responses to diseases and parasites (e.g., varroa mite), which pose severe threats to these species but can also alter the honey they produce. The obtained results will be integrated with other parameters previously collected, such as feeding rates or bee's behaviour, providing key insights and measures that can be disseminated to farmers, helping them to adopt measures that can reduce the impact of pesticides on these key pollinators. Applying these measures is expected to increase both the quality and quantity of the ecosystem services provided by bees, which will be reflected in farmers' income.

References

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Acknowledgements

Nuno G. C. Ferreira was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) through 2021.02111.CEECIND (DOI: 10.54499/2021.02111.CEECIND/CP1665/CT0003). FCT also supported this work within the scope of UIDB/04423/2020, UIDP/04423/2020 and Project BEESNESS (DOI:10.54499/CIRCNA/BRB/0293/201).

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